

Determination of Dissociation Constants of 5-Nitrosalicylic Acid and Formation Constants of Zinc (II)-5-Nitrosalicylate

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The dissociation constants of 5-nitrosalicylic acid (5NSA) have been calculated employing Bjerrum's method as followed by Martell *et al.*^{1,2}, and also by Irving-Rossotti method³. From these values the formation constants of Zn-5-nitrosalicylate have been calculated adopting the aforementioned methods.

In the investigation of the formation constants of metal complexes formed by 5NSA, following the above mentioned methods, it is necessary to determine the first and second dissociation constants of the ligand. This has been done in the present investigation employing the aforementioned methods. The formation constants of Zn(II)-5-nitrosalicylate have been determined. The literature does not reveal the values of dissociation constants of 5NSA and the formation constants of Zn(II)-5-nitrosalicylate for the purpose of comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of either B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or equivalent quality.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salts were prepared in double-distilled water.

pH of the solutions was measured by using 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter.

In the experimental set-up procedure and method of calculation are the same as described in the previous communication⁴.

Correction for pH-measurements in aqueous-dioxan solutions have been made as described by Van Uitert and Haas⁵.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interaction of zinc ions with 5NSA has caused considerable lowering of pH and a pH-metric titration of 1 : 1 metal-ligand system with alkali has revealed an inflection at two equivalents of alkali. This obviously indicates that both, carboxylic and phenolic, protons of 5NSA are quite readily liberated as a result of the chelate formation. The chelation reaction may be represented as :

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pH-metric titrations of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures of Zn^{2+} and 5NSA with alkali show inflection at four equivalents of alkali which correspond to the formation of 1 : 2 complex between Zn^{2+} and 5NSA as represented by the following equation :

The required acid dissociation constants of the carboxylic and phenolic protons of 5NSA were calculated by the above mentioned methods and are given in the Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1
NaOH 1.0*N*, 5NSA 0.025*M*.

Alkali ml.	pH	$[H^+] \times 10^3$	$b \times 10^3$	$C_A \times 10^3$	$K_1 \times 10^3$
0.00	2.40	3.981	0.3997	8.000	—
0.02	2.42	3.802	0.7995	7.997	4.209
0.04	2.45	3.548	1.1990	7.995	4.229
0.06	2.47	3.388	1.5972	7.991	4.566
0.08	2.50	3.162	1.9960	7.987	4.672
0.10	2.52	3.020	3.1900	7.986	5.339

Mean $K_1 = 4.583 \times 10^{-3}$.

TABLE 2

Alkali ml.	pH	$b \times 10^3$	$C_A \times 10^3$	$[H^+] \times 10^{11}$	$[OH^-] \times 10^4$	$[HA] \times 10^3$	$K_2 \times 10^{11}$
0.57	10.10	11.27	7.911	7.943	1.259	4.6780	5.490
0.59	10.30	11.64	7.907	5.012	1.996	4.3736	4.050
0.60	10.35	11.86	7.905	4.467	2.237	4.1723	3.986
0.62	10.45	12.25	7.902	3.548	2.817	3.8360	3.760
0.64	10.50	12.64	7.900	3.162	3.163	3.4762	3.752
0.66	10.60	13.02	7.896	2.512	3.981	3.1700	3.744

Mean $K_2 = 4.13 \times 10^{-11}$.

The values of pK_{a1} and pK_{a2} have also been obtained from the formation curve, graphical method (half neutralization point) and also by Irving-Rossotti method. The values were found to be in good agreement (vide, Table 3). The variation in values of pK_a is found to be ± 0.03 .

TABLE 3

Method	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}
Stepwise Calculation	2.33	10.38
Bjerrum	2.38	10.40
Graphical (Half Neutralization Point)	2.38	—
Irving-Rossotti	2.38	10.40

The degrees of formation of the zinc(II)-5-nitrosalicylate complexes, \bar{n} were calculated from the *pH*-titration curves. In calculating the values of \bar{n} and $[A^{2-}]$ the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. In this way a series of values of \bar{n} and $[A^{2-}]$, corresponding to different values of *pH* were obtained in each case.

The formation curve was drawn by plotting \bar{n} against $p[A^{2-}]$. The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ were directly read from the formation curve. The standard deviations of the results have been calculated by the method of least-square. The variations in the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ are found to be ± 0.02 , ± 0.05 and ± 0.06 respectively. The results have been recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4

*Formation Constants of Zn(II)-5-Nitrosalicylate*Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$, Ionic Str. = 0.1M

Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Bjerrum	6.70	6.32	13.04
Irving-Rossotti	6.65	6.25	13.00
Least-Square	6.63	6.22	12.95

The values of the formation constants (Table 4) are the Concentration Stability Constants. Although the values obtained by the method of least-square would be more acceptable, it may be seen that the Irving-Rossotti values are also representative values of the formation constants.

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REFERENCES

1. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.
2. S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
3. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
4. P. V. Khadikar and R. L. Ameria, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 33.
5. L. G. van Uitert and C. G. Haas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.

